
Postcard from Tenerife: Trade winds, climate change and tales of fragility and resilience

Join me on a journey from the breezy shores of Tenerife to the far-reaching effects of climate change and other man-made catastrophes.

Postcard from Tenerife. [Source and typo: DALL-E.](#)

Trade winds and the European colonization of America

Did you know that the word “trade” as in commerce is connected to “[trade winds](#)”? I didn’t. I was quite surprised to find out that the etymology of trade winds traces back to “blowing trade” as in sustained, persistent wind, in contrast to a breeze. Because the trade winds, or easterlies, that blow from the coast of Africa to the Americas were so critical to the colonial

expansion of Europeans, the word trade became synonymous with commercial exchange in the usage we're most familiar with.

< **trade** *n.* (compare **trade** *n.* A.I) + **wind** *n.*¹, apparently after *to blow trade* at **trade** *adv.*

With sense 3 compare earlier **breeze** *n.*² 1.

Notes

Although the name was originally unconnected with uses of *trade* with reference to commerce (see **trade** *n.* A.III), the importance of such winds (especially the constant winds near the equator) to commercial navigation eventually led to these senses being associated.

[Oxford English Dictionary, s.v. “trade wind \(n.\), Etymology,” June 2024.](#)

Interestingly, other languages don't use “trade” for commerce. The French use the word “[alizé](#)” for trade wind and thus never adopted a French version for trade, with the translation being simply “commerce”. One funny anecdote about “[alizé](#)” is how the city of Privas in Ardèche, France, decided to christen its main street as “[Avenue des Champs Alizés](#)” in a humorous nod to its more famous Parisian counterpart. Any connection between the tropical winds and the town of Privas or Ardèche in general remains a mystery. One has to conclude that the city council came up with the pun and thought it was too good to pass.

The Trade winds (in yellow). [Source: Wikipedia.](#)

The [trade winds](#) were basically what enabled Europeans to colonize the Americas, with all the upheaval we know. The Spanish ships, known as “[Galeón de Manila](#),” relied on these winds to sail across the Atlantic and [couldn't sail into the wind](#). Imagine how different world history would be if these winds blew from west to east instead. There might be no [Latin America](#) as we know it, and [La Copa América](#) would not have the passion and fervor of its Spanish and Portuguese influences that it has today. Climate does shape history and our lives.

[The passionate style of South American football is a reflection of its Latin cultural influences. Here is an example from Copa America 2024.](#)

Postcard from Tenerife

Why am I writing about trade winds? I'm currently in the [Atlantic ocean island of Tenerife](#) for some chill time and on a writing/catchup retreat of sorts. This place is a natural history heaven and perhaps more than any other island, it has inspired scientists ever since [Alexander von Humboldt set foot here and climbed Mount Teide](#). You can read all about Humboldt in [the fabulous book "The Invention of Nature" by Andrea Wulf](#). He is credited with laying the foundations for the field of biogeography, and his observations on the interconnectedness of nature were groundbreaking. Humboldt was also aware of the impact of climate on life, noting how changes in temperature and altitude affected the distribution of plant species.

[“The Invention of Nature” by Andrea Wulf.](#)

As Andrea Wulf wrote in her book, in the aftermath of World War II, Alexander von Humboldt’s monumental contributions to science were often overlooked, given the Western tendency to redefine intellectual legacies in their favor. This erasure highlights the tendency for those in power to rewrite narratives, often to the detriment of key historical figures whose identities do not align with post-war ideologies. However, [Wulf’s biography](#) and other recent scholarship has begun to restore Humboldt’s rightful place in the annals of scientific history, recognizing his profound influence on our understanding of the natural world.

Charles Darwin, who read Humboldt’s work, [desperately wanted to visit Tenerife](#). Instead, he got stuck on board the HMS Beagle as the ship was ordered to quarantine for 12 days due to fears of cholera. Captain FitzRoy, in his decisive manner, wouldn’t take it and elected to sail on. No Tenerife for Darwin. Instead, he sailed on with the trade winds to the Americas, ultimately getting his inspiration from the Galápagos Islands rather than the Canaries.

[HMS Beagle as it would have appeared on the shores of Santa Cruz, Tenerife.](#)

The unique climate of Tenerife

The impact of climate is so evident here in [Tenerife](#). These islands are off the coast of North Africa, literally just a few hundred kilometers away. Yet instead of scorching July weather, we have a pleasant, breezy, balmy 25°C with clouds often accumulating throughout the night and mornings. That's what the combination of trade winds and volcanic islands gives you: pleasant weather with the clouds providing much-needed moisture when the winds hit the mountains. As the air rises and cools, it condenses into clouds that accumulate at mid-altitude, creating a stunning visual effect of a vast, undulating sea of clouds. In Tenerife, this phenomenon known as the "sea of clouds" ([mar de nubes](#)) is a breathtaking sight, often visible from the slopes of Mount Teide. This natural spectacle not only offers a picturesque view but also plays a crucial role in the island's microclimate, providing essential moisture to the diverse ecosystems on Tenerife.

[Mar de nubes as seen in Tenerife.](#)

Not that far from here, you have the [Sahara](#), that vast inhospitable land, covered with dust. Occasionally, as the trade winds blow from there, you get Sahara dust reaching the Canary Islands and beyond. [The locals call this phenomenon “calima,” and it affects the weather significantly, sometimes causing hazy skies and reducing air quality. This dust can even travel as far as Florida](#), resulting in gorgeous sunsets and episodes of air pollution.

[NASA Earth Observatory images illustrating the Sahara dust storms known as calima.](#)

[Calima: When Sahara dust reaches the Canary Islands.](#)

How will the trade winds be affected by climate change?

It's evident that the climate is changing. In nearby North Africa, the trend is already a major source of concern, with increasing desertification and water scarcity posing significant challenges. In fact, [the Middle East and North Africa \(MENA\) region is viewed as the most water-stressed region in the world](#), with [sixteen of the twenty-five most water-stressed countries located there](#).

[83% of the population in the Middle East and North Africa \(MENA\) is exposed to extremely high water stress.](#)

In Tenerife, like other oceanic islands, the unique geography means that the impact of climate change might be tempered by the buffering influence of the cold ocean water. In some model simulations, which include representations of the ocean, atmosphere, land processes, and sea ice in the North and South poles, [the authors noted a strengthening of the tropical trade winds](#). Additionally, stronger trade winds can drive more heat into the ocean, [potentially stalling the impact of climate change in the short term](#). Inevitably, climate change will affect the island. Rising sea levels, changing precipitation patterns, and increasing temperatures are all concerns that could impact Tenerife's unique ecosystems and weather patterns.

The future will tell how these winds, so crucial to our past, will shape the future. What we do know is that understanding and adapting to these changes is crucial for the well-being of humankind.

The paradoxical fragility and resilience that define human history

[Los Guanches: the indigenous people of Tenerife who trace back to North African Berber Amazighs.](#)

What we also know is that we haven't learned the lessons of the past. When the Spanish arrived in 1494, [an estimated 30,000 Guanches](#)—[the indigenous people](#)—lived in Tenerife. Their story mirrors other genocidal wars. The Guanches are now confined to museums [where you can witness their mummified remains](#). But their legacy still lives on in their genes, as [a good fraction of Canary Islanders have DNA signatures of North African Berber Amazighs](#). Is this the fate of humankind, to persist somehow despite wars, genocides, and climate upheaval?

[The astonishing story of the Guanche Mummies on Tenerife Island.](#)

Reflecting on the Guanches' fate, I am reminded of the paradoxical fragility and resilience that define human history. This resilience is constantly tested by our inability to fully grasp and address the long-term consequences of our actions. The current climate crisis, much like the historical and modern conquests and genocides, poses a monumental challenge that requires us to learn from our past and act decisively for our future. As we stand on the brink of significant environmental and political change, we must ask ourselves whether we will finally heed the lessons of history or continue to repeat the mistakes that have led to the downfall of countless civilizations before us.

The paradoxical fragility and resilience that define human history. [Source: DALL-E.](#)

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Natural History of Tenerife

Philip Ashmole, Myrtle Ashmole

- An authoritative and lavishly illustrated account of the nature of Tenerife
- Describes the distinctive habitats on the island and illustrates the plants typical of each of them
- Includes descriptions and access information on over 40 sites where the special animals and plants can be seen in natural conditions
- Provides full information on the birds, mammals, reptiles, butterflies and dragonflies of the island
- Explains the geological, evolutionary and ecological processes that gave rise to the modern island with its unique flora and fauna
- A truly essential book for local naturalists and those visiting Tenerife

[Natural History of Tenerife](#) by Philip Ashmole and Myrtle Ashmole